

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF SAFFLOWER OIL IN TOXIC HEPATITIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17118516>

Relevance: Toxic hepatitis represents a pressing issue in hepatology due to hepatocyte damage caused by chemical and drug intoxication. A critical mechanism of this pathology is oxidative stress, accompanied by lipid peroxidation and a decrease in endogenous antioxidant defense [2, 3]. Natural hepatoprotective agents with antioxidant properties are highly relevant because existing pharmacological therapies often have side effects. Safflower oil, rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids and bioactive compounds, is considered a promising candidate for correcting oxidative imbalance [1, 4]. However, experimental data regarding its efficiency in toxic hepatitis remain limited. Studying its effect on antioxidant parameters is essential for substantiating its clinical potential [5, 6].

Aim of the study: To evaluate the antioxidant activity of safflower oil in comparison with cottonseed oil in experimental toxic hepatitis.

Materials and Methods: The study included 40 male outbred rats divided into intact, control, safflower oil, and cottonseed oil groups (n = 5 in each). Acute toxic hepatitis was induced by intragastric administration of paracetamol (1000 mg/kg). Starting from day 3, animals received daily oral doses of safflower or cottonseed oil (10 ml/kg) for 14 days. Biochemical parameters were measured using enzyme immunoassay kits, including malondialdehyde (MDA), catalase, and superoxide dismutase (SOD). Statistical analysis was performed with Student's t-test ($p < 0.05$ considered significant).

Results: In the control group, MDA levels increased by 1.3-fold compared to intact animals, reflecting intensified lipid peroxidation. Administration of safflower oil reduced MDA by 1.17 times versus control ($p < 0.05$), whereas cottonseed oil lowered it by 1.16 times. Catalase activity, which decreased 1.53-fold in control rats, was restored 1.29-fold with safflower oil and 1.31-fold with cottonseed oil compared to control. SOD activity was suppressed in control animals by 1.21-fold relative to intact. Treatment with safflower oil increased SOD activity by 1.13-fold, and cottonseed oil by 1.12-fold. Although both oils demonstrated antioxidant activity, safflower oil provided slightly stronger correction of oxidative stress parameters. These findings confirm the role of safflower oil in reducing oxidative injury in hepatocytes.

Conclusions: Safflower oil demonstrated significant antioxidant activity by lowering MDA and restoring enzymatic defense. Its effects were more pronounced compared to cottonseed oil, particularly in enhancing SOD and catalase activity. Correction of oxidative imbalance underlies the hepatoprotective action of safflower oil. The results justify its potential inclusion as a natural antioxidant in dietary and therapeutic protocols for liver disorders. Further clinical studies are needed to establish optimal dosages and long-term effects.

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